

Queer Politics Might Be Exactly Where We Need to Search for Answers on Palestine

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As a researcher of LGBTQ politics in Palestine and the wider MENA region, I often encounter bewildered looks when discussing the growing ‘Queers for Palestine’ movement. Questions like “*Do gay people exist in Palestine?*” and “*shouldn’t they be supporting Israel for being more LGBTQ friendly?*” reveal commonplace flawed assumptions: that Queer and Palestinian identities are antithetical, and that national liberation struggles necessitate the subordination of other social struggles.

A cursory search on Palestine and Palestinians in mainstream political science publishing outlets reveals serious limitation in our understanding of intersectional oppression and Palestinian political life more generally. Where Palestine is invoked in recently published works, the research tended to obscure Palestinian identity and agency, mislabel self-identifying Palestinians as Israeli Arabs, and frame contentious intergroup relations within a reductive minority framework. With few notable exceptions, Palestinian politics rarely surfaced outside the confines of discussions of anger, hostility, frustrations, and ‘ethnically based terrorism.’

But turning our attention to emerging spaces within the discipline, particularly the field of

Queer politics can provide historical nuance to how we understand marginalization, solidarity, and intersectional mobilization within the context of occupied Palestine.

New research on LGBTQ mobilization highlights the centrality of political solidarity to Queer movements historically. Zein Murib’s book, *Terms of Exclusion*, illustrates how the early gay movement constructed its identity historically “by linking gay people with Black Panther, antiwar, Women’s Liberation, and Communist movements” (2024, 40). The movement cemented the idea that all forms of marginalization are the product of “intertwined ideologies of sexism, racism, capitalism, and imperialism” (Murib 2024, 40). In the early 1970s, Gay Liberationists insisted on defining queerness as “political praxis” rather than a mere “expression of sexuality,” paving the way for today’s resurgence of anti-liberal Queer Liberationist thinking.

Queers for Palestine reflects a growing political consciousness among young LGBTQ+ groups in response to the nation-state’s violence against marginalized people. Queer communities are acutely aware of the links between the cascade of laws targeting trans individuals and the mounting legal pressures to silence pro-Palestine advocacy. Since the war on Gaza began, LGBTQ people have watched with concern how the same liberal

regimes that claim to champion human rights and celebrate LGBTQ+ people are the ones rushing to resupply Israel's war coalition with weapons. And since the war started, Queer communities have been at the heart of Palestine solidarity organizing to demand a ceasefire and stand up against liberal pinkwashing (Atshan 2023). And the divides over defining queer identity we saw in the seventies have appeared once more as Queer activists recently protested outside the Human Rights Campaign annual Gala to oppose their ties to weapon manufacturers (Factora 2024).

What's more, liberal politicians have been publicly attacking pro-Palestine protestors and framing them as a fifth column of Putin (Guo 2024), in a way that evokes the lavender scare of the 1950s, and the subsequent demonization of Queer people as communist subversives. It is, thus, no surprise that Queer people are drawing on a long tradition of viewing Queerness as a 'commitment to solidarity' with all oppressed people whose fates are intertwined, and a rejection of liberalism's use as a coverup to the violence against Queer people, Palestinians, and those at the intersection.

When power asymmetries produce such horrific injustice, we, political scientists, can also seek inspiration from the Queer tradition of viewing identity as political praxis, and that includes our professional identities as scholars of politics. Our pursuit of objectivity and value neutrality as essential to studying politics as a science should leave room for Queer and feminist epistemologies or 'ways of knowing' that do not privilege knowledge production about the marginalized, but for them (McHugh 2014). The strict quest for value neutrality in what we produce has proven damaging to our ability to speak to this moment and to challenge it. Perhaps worse, it

has led many among us to remain silent. ♦

References

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